

The Perception of the Message against the Cigarette "Smoking is Injurious to Health" by Consumers of Matete in Kinshasa (Message Contained On Cigarette Packaging)

Christ Selle MASAKALE, PhD student at the University of Kinshasa
Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences
Department of Information and Communication Sciences

Abstract:- It is a question in this research, to analyze the perception of the message "Smoking is detrimental to health" by Kinshasa consumers, especially those of Matete. Message contained on the packaging or on the packets of cigarettes. We resorted first to the theory of perception, second to persuasive communication and to the theory of effects.

We started from the observation that despite this message or this warning, Kinshasa consumers in general and those of Matete in particular continue to smoke cigarettes. After interview and interpretation of the results, we found that this message on the packaging is not enough. For effective tobacco control we suggest: limiting the level of nicotine and tar in cigarettes; consumer information through tobacco control advertisements and awareness through personal communication; the protection of non-smokers by banning smoking in places of public use.

I. INTRODUCTION

The DRC is a country where there are many cigarette consumers, without realizing the consequences that flow from it. According to a press release published the day before No Tobacco Day in 2007, Margaret Chan, Director General of the WHO, reminded the population that tobacco smoke contains around 4,000 chemical substances, of which more than 50 are carcinogenic. According to the WHO, 200,000 workers die each year as a result of passive smoking at work and around 700 million children breathe air polluted by tobacco smoke. The WHO asks all countries that have not yet taken measures to take action to protect the population¹. Some countries like France have decided to no longer allow smoking in public, but the DRC has only succeeded in requiring tobacco companies to mark their packaging with the words: "Smoking is detrimental to health".

Today in Kinshasa we see a high number of smokers in all social strata; the majorities of them do not care about their health and often suffer from diseases such as tuberculosis. They have a slogan saying: what's the point of dying with healthy lungs, even if I don't die of tuberculosis,

I will end up dying of another disease. They consume cigarettes in excess, often without eating, without worrying about their health and that of others.

Our study takes a look at the perception that Matete smokers have of the message: "SMOKING IS HARMFUL TO HEALTH", after a large number of experiences, we ask ourselves the following research questions:

- How do smokers in Matete perceive the message or warning "Smoking is harmful to health"?
- What attitude do they adopt when faced with this message?

To the questions asked, one would think that by observing smokers, we have the esteem conviction that this message really does not reach their consciences, this message has no impact on consumers in general, they do not feel challenged or pay attention to this message on the packaging. The cigarette has taken a position of identity in such a way that despite the message, consumers do not abandon this practice.

This study is first of all part of the theory of perception which can be understood following SCAILLET as an awareness of an object or an external fact which has caused more or less numerous sensory excitations in us. and complex.²This theory will allow us to understand how this population perceives this message. Perception is described here as a process because it is the result of visual and auditory processing. The perception of such an object is the result of the processing of retinal executions. This treatment happens in a period of time, the perception is constructive.

Perception is the identification of figures. Indeed, it is not automatic because a stimulus must first be interpreted, recognized in order to have subsequent effects. Perception is related to the characteristics of people who depend on:

- The history of each individual, social classes, profession, usual activities, culture, lifestyle, etc.
- The attitudinal predispositions which indicate the conscious or unconscious preoccupations of each one.

¹ News. Un. Org OMS : Seules des environnements 100 % sans fumée protègent efficacement contre les dangers du tabagisme passif, Consulté le 06-08-2022, 12h15.

² S.SCAILLET, *Psychologie appliquée à l'éducation*, Franciscaire missionnaires de Marie, Paris, 1981.

Then, our study is also in line with the thought of J.N.KAPFERER³ who, for him, persuasive communication is the process of attitude change that is done by the transmission of linguistic symbols or not. It is on the basis of this theory that we are going to make a communication for behavior change in order to provide solutions to this problem. To succeed in confirming or invalidating all the hypotheses mentioned above, we resorted to the ethnographic method which, according to Christian Ghasarian⁴, consists in fact of a descent into the field carried out by an investigator who "Lives with and like" those he studies. Our ethnographic investigation was accompanied by the techniques of in-depth interview and participant observation.

Given the importance of the subject studied, we develop the following three essential points:

- General information on the cigarette concept;
- The perception of the message against cigarettes: "smoking is detrimental to health" by consumers of Matete in Kinshasa. Message contained on the packaging of cigarettes;
- Perspectives of behavior change communication.

II. GENERALITY ON THE CIGARETTE CONCEPT

A. History of cigarettes

The cigarette owes its history to tobacco. Tobacco is a plant close to the tomato, of Latin American origin. This plant is endowed with a bitter and toxic substance: nicotine. It was discovered by Christophe COLOMB. Its culture spread very early in Europe and at that time, it was exploited as a medicinal plant capable of calming migraines. The success of tobacco today is linked to the invention of the cigarette. Indeed, the transformation of tobacco into cigarettes dates back to around 1843 with the beginning of industrialization. And the use of cigarettes spread from the 1860s with the birth of the first brands. Smoking increased sharply in several European and African countries in 1910 and in the Democratic Republic of Congo around 1911 through the B.A.T. (British American Tobacco) company, the current TABACONGO.⁵

B. Cigarette consumer

For J.V.PETROF, the consumer is a person who seeks to satisfy various needs through the acquisition of goods and who, during the process of self-satisfaction, destroys or diminishes the usefulness of these goods⁶.

³ J.N.KAPFERER, *Les chemins de la persuasion : mode d'influence des media et de la publicité sur les comportements*, Paris, Gauthier-Vilars, 1978.

⁴ C. GHASARIAN, *De l'ethnographie à l'anthropologie réflexive, Nouveaux terrains, nouvelles pratiques, nouveaux enjeux*, Paris, Armand Colin Editeur, 2004.

⁵ MULAMBA NDAMBU, *La lutte antitabac en RDC*, Mémoire, IFASIC, 1999-2000.

⁶ J.V.PETROF, *Comportement du consommateur et marketing*, 5e édition, Quebec, les presses de l'université LAVAL, 1993, p.3.

A distinction has been made between the concept of consumer, buyer and customer.

- A consumer is one who buys and consumes;
- The buyer may not be the one who consumes but only buys;
- The customer is a regular buyer.

C. Composition of the cigarette

For Jean-François CLOUTIER, the harmfulness of cigarettes and their smoke is due to their chemical composition, which includes around 4,000 different substances, 40 of which are the main responsible for their toxicity. Secondary cigarette smoke contains six times more nicotine, three times more tar, and seventy times more ammonia than in the smoke installed by the smoker.⁷

Indeed, the components most often declared are nicotine and tar; while laboratory analysis shows that with natural tobacco leaves, there are thousands of additives that are associated, the number of which varies from one brand to another.

D. The effects of Tobacco (Cigarette)

The harmful effects of tobacco also concern non-smokers living in the entourage of a smoker. Tobacco is the second leading cause of death in the world and if current trends in its consumption continue by 2020, the number of deaths due to smoking would reach ten million in the developing country. Can distinguish between passive and active smoker.

a) Active smoker

It is perceived at three levels:

- The way of smoking: inhalation is probably the most important factor with regard to the risks of lung cancer;
- The number of cigarettes consumed per day influences the nature of the risk;
- The type of consumption: the duration and intensity of smoking; the time factor is not surprising knowing that infections generally only appear after 10 to 20 years.

b) Passive smoker

He is a non-smoker but only breathes the air polluted by the smoke emitted by active smokers.⁸ This presentation of the cigarette, although brief, allows us to understand the rationality of a fight against tobacco.

E. The Origins of the Rule "Smoking is detrimental to health" in the DRC

The Democratic Republic of Congo, a member of the WHO, is also committed to the fight against tobacco. On October 25, 2002, Mr. KIKAYA KARUBI, then Minister of Communication and Press, signed Ministerial Order No. 04/MCP/009/2002 which legislates on Tobacco.

⁷ J.F. CLOUTIER, *La composition des cigarettes et les carcinomes pulmonaires*, thèse, www.Ulval.ca.

⁸ *Idem*

In its article 5, the decree prohibits all forms of television and radio advertising. It also prohibits any form of tobacco product advertising in the print media. It is recommended that producers include on each packet of cigarettes the name of the brand, the nicotine and tar contents as well as the health warning "Smoking is detrimental to health". The decree still applies today.⁹

F. La Motivation

For J.V.PETROF¹⁰, the term motivation refers to all the factors that determine behavior. It is oriented towards the achievement of goals that can satisfy such needs. It is linked to two aspects of behavior:

- The objective pursued;
- The energy expended to reach it.

There are three phases in the consumer motivation process:

- The need;
- The behaviour ;
- The goal.

a) The need

According to the author, there are two categories of needs, namely biogenetic needs and psychogenic needs. A biogenetic need is created by a physiological imbalance or lack. Psychogenic needs are of a different nature and generally result from the contact of human beings with their socio-cultural environment.

b) The behaviour

Not all human behavior is necessarily motivated, but consumer behavior usually is. When the consumer reaches this second phase, it is the signals he receives from the environment that determine the nature and direction of his behavior, because he will have been influenced.

c) The goal

The third phase of the motivation process is the goal. All motivated behavior is goal-directed and once that goal is achieved, the motivational process ends.

III. PERCEPTION OF THE MESSAGE CONTAINED ON CIGARETTE PACKAGING: "SMOKING IS INJURIOUS TO HEALTH" BY CONSUMERS OF MATETE IN KINSHASA

A. Description of participants

To achieve the purpose of the interview, which is to understand the perception of consumers of Matete in relation to the message contained on the packaging of cigarettes, we interviewed them. As part of our interviews, we used a random sample which is part of the representative samples. Our sample size is 30 people, since our technique does not require large numbers. The interviews used are best placed for ethnographic studies.

⁹Idem

¹⁰ J.V.PETROF, *op.cit.*, p.59-61.

Our sample is made up of a fair average comprising adults whose age varies between 18 and 60 years. We have represented them this way:

- Male, executive in a local company: 51 years old.
- Male, military officer: 32 years old.
- Student: 19 years old.
- Retired man: 69 years old
- Merchant: 26 years old
- Male, executive in a local company: 36 years old
- Woman without a job: 28 years old
- Free woman: 30 years old
- Seller of cigarettes: 30 years
- Free woman: 28 years old.
- Male, military officer: 35 years old.
- Male, executive in a local company: 41 years old.
- Free woman: 25 years old.
- Student: 22 years old.
- Shopkeeper: 46 years old.
- Free woman: 33 years old.
- Cigarette seller: 38 years old.
- Student: 21 years old.
- Female agent in a local company: 27 years old.
- Woman without a job: 32 years old.
- Shopkeeper: 29 years old.
- Shopkeeper: 39 years old.
- Man, agent in a company: 35 years old.
- Tradesman: 24 years old.
- Retired man: 71 years old.
- Cigarette seller: 41 years old.
- Shopkeeper: 33 years old.
- Male agent in a company: 29 years old.
- Woman without a job: 40 years old.
- Cigarette seller: 45 years old.

B. Interview prompt questions

- Why do you smoke?
- How many rods/Packets do you take per day?
- Since you started smoking, have you suffered from a disease caused by smoking?
- Are you aware of the message "Smoking is harmful to health" mentioned in cigarette packaging?
- What is your perception of this message?
- What attitude do you adopt towards this message?
- Do you think that this message on packaging is an effective way to reduce the rate of smokers?
- If not, what are the means that you can propose to reduce the rate of smokers?

C. Grouping of synthetic results

The purpose of this point is to make a synthetic grouping of the results that were produced by our interviews. We have grouped the findings into four main themes:

Theme 1: Motivation for consumption and frequency.

Topic 2: Diseases related to cigarette smoking.

Theme 3: Knowledge of the message "Smoking is detrimental to health" and its perception.

Theme 4: The effectiveness of the message used for sensitization and the attitude adopted towards this message.

Topic 5: Suggestion on raising awareness on cigarette packaging.

D. Motivation for consumption and frequency

In terms of motivation, we recorded several responses. For smokers, it is therefore simple pleasure, to relax, out of habit and finally to have a good appetite. The participants gave varied answers in relation to their frequency of smoking. But we can remember that the majority of participants often claim to consume 10 stems per day.

- a) Illnesses related to cigarette smoking
All of our stakeholders say they know the consequences of cigarette smoking. Some have already experienced this but others have not.
- b) Knowledge of the message "Smoking is detrimental to health" mentioned in cigarette packaging and its perception among consumers
The majority of our stakeholders said they had seen this message before. Nine out of thirty did not recognize her. With regard to the perception of the message with the public, it results that it is a message which prohibits smoking, it is a message which shows the dangers of the cigarette, it is a message to discourage the smokers, It is a preventive message.
- c) The effectiveness of the message used for sensitization and the attitude adopted towards this message.
The majority of participants think that this message is not very effective because despite this mention the smoking rate is still increasing as well as the mortality rate. As for the attitude adopted towards the message, many are those who have understood the importance of the message and say they are already used to eating them, others still say to themselves that they take it or not they will die, why die with healthy lungs.
- d) Awareness suggestion for cigarette packaging
All the participants think that it is a good message but it is not effective for the change of behavior because the tool by which this communication is done is not enough, it is necessary that it is other means more effective such as television, radio, posters, in short, strong awareness.

IV. COMMUNICATION FOR BEHAVIOR CHANGE

In our proposal of communication for change, we appeal to two theories namely: theory of persuasion and theory of effects. These two theories were popularized by Jean Noel Kapferer. These two theories according to the conception of the author, are associative and complementary.

A. Persuasive communication for changing smoking behavior

We reported earlier that the message "smoking is injurious to health" is a good message to prevent the consequences of smoking, only that the only way of interpretation contained on the package does not attract the

attention of smokers in depending on several reasons including: understanding of the message, literacy, lack of attention, etc.

From the above, the exploration of persuasion is therefore essential in the psychological process by which it is useful to sensitize and change the opinions, feelings, intentions and behaviors of smokers in general and those of Matete in particular.

The study of persuasion can be done from three angles: that of the structure of the media, the content of the messages and the effects of the communications. The first approach is sociological and political. Investigators typically address the following questions: who controls the information, who owns the media, how do certain groups influence the dissemination of information? The second approach is entirely concerned with the latent content: what are the values conveyed the current signs and symbols? It brings together linguistics, semantics, semiotics and cultural anthropology¹¹.

Indeed, Kapferer's theory of persuasion aims to allow the researcher a systematic mastery of the communication environment, in particular advertising. This theory therefore makes it possible to better immerse oneself in the context that prevails for:

- Make available to the public a correct, complete, clear and coherent message;
- Make him accept this message;
- Arouse in him a lasting change of behavior;
- Avoid "congenital" errors with regard to communication (that of believing that communication is a field without solidly established rules, that is to say that can be done anyhow and that of believing in the whole power of the mass media as if mass communication alone is enough to change behavior)¹².

Indeed, to understand the behavior of smokers, it is important to understand the context in which it evolves. If the context is not clearly distinguished, acknowledged and confronted, changes of fundamental importance cannot occur. For Kapferer, the theory of the "omnipotence" of "mass media" is not enough on its own to change the behavior of the receiving public, even if in our contemporary societies a message to produce more widespread effects and reach an audience numerous, generally passes through the mass media. Its effectiveness should therefore be put into perspective¹³.

The role of social circles, groups, guides and opinion leaders, direct contacts, i.e. interpersonal communication, are also to be taken into account in the process of adopting new behaviors in individuals. . Indeed, an individual can be

¹¹ Diane NKURUNZIZA, *L'impact de la propagande sur les électeurs lors de la campagne pour les présidentielles de 2011. Cas des communes de Limete et de Masina en RDC*, mémoire, L2, IFASIC, communication et journalisme, 2011-2012.

¹² *Idem.*

¹³ *Idem.*

more influenced by his living environment and by the people who form his entourage than by the message of the mass media. Under these conditions, the “persuader” must worry about modifying the environment rather than producing a persuasive discourse intended for each individual. This observation is crucial in the case of cigarette smokers in the municipality of Matete.

Persuasion theory includes a five-step process: exposure to message, decoding of the message, acceptance of the message, generalization of the effects, and adoption of the new behavior.¹⁴ It is the change of behavior in the direction of the sender's intention. We will try to apply these steps in our proposal to change the behavior of tobacco smokers living in the municipality of Matete.

- a) Exposure to the message
The message to be studied here is this: “Smoking is detrimental to health”.

Fig. 1: Exposure to the message

The main reasons that should lead the issuer (WHO, Congolese State and TOBACCO companies) to expose this message are: lexical or linguistic obstacles, lack of profit, poor choice of media or of the sole medium for exposing the message "the wrapper", the intellectual level of the receiver of the messages who is Matete's smoker. Note at this level that:

- The message "smoking is detrimental to health" is not always targeted, that is to say, developed according to the psychology and values specific to each target, in our case, the smoker in Matete. From where it would be necessary to adapt this message to the psychology of the smokers who are the majority of the children of the street and the delinquents commonly called KULUNA, thus the drivers and the receivers of public transport and motorcyclists;
- Communication vehicles from different social backgrounds are generally little used. The message should also be conveyed in national languages, rather than in French, because the large numbers of consumers do not speak French.

Lingala: “Komela likaya eza koboma bokolongono bwa nzoto”:

- Social constraints such as inequalities in wealth, occupation or location are generally not taken into account. This question is up to policy makers. The fight against unemployment in the municipality of Matete is also the fight against the disordered consumption of cigarettes. It should be noted that the greatest consumption takes place in stables at a point of sale when smokers have nothing to do. For this, every day we register new smokers by influence of the old ones of the stable. Smoking becomes a sine qua non for belonging to such and such a stable. Each level and quantity of consumption gives the granting of a grade to another. In Matete we have the following grades:

- Beginner: mobandeli;
- The regular or professional: momeli;
- The veteran: mbiaka.
- ❖ Communication strategies are often limited to media aspects alone, neglecting non-media actions. However, the real sensitization of Matete smokers should be done through interpersonal communication, by sending sensitization groups to lecture on the consequences of tobacco and the reasons or key moments for its consumption. This communication should be done through social groups, churches, centers of education and initiation to new citizenship, schools, sports groups, etc.

- b) Decoding the message

This is the stage of communication of the message by the receiver, i.e. the smoker. It is the relationship between the meaning attributed by the source and the meaning attributed by the public.

The message "smoking is detrimental to health" experiences a margin of ambiguity that does not allow the majority of smokers to decode the message. According to the answers obtained by our interviews, some smokers think that the term "detrimental" would mean "appreciable", "beautiful", "good", for this category, "smoking is appreciable to health", that is to say that is, for them, the tobacco companies sell their products by inviting the public to mass consumption. Yet the message says the opposite of what they think. Hence it was necessary to facilitate the understanding of the message by:

- A short explanation of the message;
- A conception of the message using vulgar, clear, ordinary, non-medical or scientific terms;
- A mention of chemical compounds;
- Write in the language the consumer understands: Lingala for example;
- In the cultural context. Smoking in the Kinshasa context most often refers to uneducated and poorly educated people;
- The image of a sickly coughing rather than a healthy footballer (see the image above), etc.

¹⁴Idm.

c) Acceptance or not of the message

In our case, the majority of interviewees do not accept the sender's message "smoking is detrimental to health". This is due to multiple reasons: social (unemployment, educational level, economic situation, family and company factors). The message also seems unacceptable due to the prejudices that smokers have of tobacco and integrated into their daily lives. Here are some of the prejudices they make to themselves to boycott the sender's message:

- What's the use of dying with weak lungs" that is to say, even if I don't die of a disease caused by the toxic effect of cigarettes, I will die of another disease. Between the dilemma of consuming and not consuming, it would be necessary to consume because the two incompatible positions lead to the same end;
- The cigarette drives away the cold, sleep and shyness", that is to say that the cigarette plays the same role as caffeine in the functioning of the human body, by stimulating strength, keeping the temperature normal, stifling drowsiness and stresses, etc.,
- The cigarette gives courage and wisdom", that is to say, the one who smokes does not fear terror, calamities and trials. He always has a way out.

It emerges from this observation that to convey the message of the change in behavior of the smokers studied and obtain the desired effects, it would be necessary to begin by changing their social and cognitive situations in which they find themselves, in particular by granting even rudimentary employment, social reintegration in a family or socialization home, raising the standard of living and economics, integrating them into a situation of self-sufficiency and self-care, etc.

d) The generalization of effects

In persuasion theory, behavioral change, cognitive, affective and intentional, refers to the situation of the person being exposed to the message, who is expected to accept the message. The cognitive component relates to opinions, while the affective and intentional component relates to evaluations and action intentions. Indeed, it is not enough to accept a communication for there to be automatically a change in behavior.

In view of the above, we encountered three categories of cigarette smokers in the municipality of Matete:

- Those who accept the content of the message "smoking is detrimental to health" and who are in favor of the recommendation formulated in the message, and finally who express the intention to apply it. They are in the minority. In this situation, the 3 components of attitude (cognitive, affective and intentional) come together and we hope to achieve behavior change in the near future;
- Those who know the content of the message "smoking is detrimental to health", but who do not experience the feeling of displaying a change in

behavior. Smokers recognize the validity of the message, but reject the recommendation, at the same time refusing the effort necessary to apply it or adopt the proposed behavior. In general, they refuse the adoption of the recommendation, the inappropriate evaluation of the consequences and the doubts of the veracity of the message, according to preconceived prejudices (see prejudices above).

- Those for whom the evaluation of the message is not accompanied by a change of intention. In this situation, they accept the content of the message "smoking is detrimental to health" but do not express the intention to follow it. The costly nature (the effort that requires following the message's recommendation) of the recommendation and the non-perception (the individual's refusal) of the implications of this recommendation are generally the two barriers that prevent these smokers from modifying their intentions.

e) Changing or adopting a new behavior

At this level, we note the absence of control or evaluation of the feedback by the sender of the message "smoking is detrimental to health" at all three levels (WHO, the State, the bricole societies) in the municipality of Matete. This should encourage the improvement and adaptation of their message to the context of the hour and the environment of smokers. For our part, the credibility of the message should be linked to the effectiveness of the testimonies of cigarette smokers. On the other hand, our observation and research on the ground show us the opposite. Communicating the message is not effective even though its content is true. Our wish would be that the message requires that its content adapts to the current needs of cigarette smokers.

B. Behavior Changing Effects

As regards the message "smoking is detrimental to health", the issuer can only set its objectives (reduce tobacco consumption, prevent tobacco-related diseases, prevent juvenile delinquency, etc.) by knowing what the effects of this message are on cigarette smokers.

a) Types of effects

a. Effects related to the medium used

Referring to our medium used, which is similar to printing and reading (written medium), we conclude from non-surveys that this medium is not able to produce the desired effects with the target population. Let us recall the population constituting the smokers of the commune of Matete, is a population having a low level of education and not mastering French to read and write. This situation does not allow the medium used or adopted to produce the desired effects.

Another glaring problem is that of the interest we have in writing, the Kinshasa community in general, and that of Matete in

particular, is not interested in reading, hence a message in writing carries little effects than that of other mediums.

From the above, we suggest that apart from the written medium (poster and packaging), interpersonal communication should be added, by proceeding with the sensitization of the groupings in sight. As a result, NGOs, socialization institutions and citizenship education associations, supported by the State, can carry the burden of awareness.

- b. Effects linked to the content of the message
Our study only addresses the moral and social effects. Regarding the moral effects, the content of the message "smoking is detrimental to health" does not at all cause the moral effects on cigarette smokers in the commune of Matete. Referring to what we said above, in the face of prejudices about tobacco consumption, the content of the message is often trivialized by smokers who find that smoking cigarettes is a non-negotiable good deal.

As for the social effects, as long as the moral effects are almost non-existent, the moral ones cannot be justified, because they are intimately linked. Hence our proposal to first change the social and environmental conditions of smokers, in order to boost both moral and social effects.

Moreover, another more effective option is to adapt the content of the message to the context and the situation where the smokers find themselves. Typical example, refer the content to a public order constraint: "smoking in public is punishable by penal servitude". The fear of public coercion would change the behavior of smokers and decrease the number of group smokers. Consumption would shift to an isolated and less interested activity.

For the smoking public of Matete, the message "smoking is detrimental to health" would produce effects only if it is adapted to these constituent characteristics which are: level of education, language, social conditions, etc. Being limited only to language, the content of the message can only produce effects if it is spoken by the vehicular languages of the target, which are Lingala, Swahili, Kikongo and Tshiluba.

V. CONCLUSION

As part of our research, it was a question of analyzing the message "Smoking is detrimental to health" by Kinshasa consumers, especially those of Matete. Message contained on the packaging or on the packets of cigarettes, in order to guide it through targeted, contextualized and effective persuasive communication.

We started from the observation that despite this message or this warning, Kinshasa consumers in general and those of Matete in particular continue to smoke cigarettes. This observation led us to ask ourselves these research questions: How does the population of Matete perceive the message or the warning "Smoking is harmful to health"? What attitude does she adopt in the face of this message?

After interview and interpretation of the results, we found that this message on the packaging is not enough. For effective tobacco control we suggest: limiting the level of nicotine and tar in cigarettes; consumer information through tobacco control advertisements and awareness through personal communication; the protection of non-smokers by banning smoking in places of public use.

REFERENCES

- [1.] CLOUTIER, J.F., *La composition des cigarettes et les carcinomes pulmonaires*, thèse, www.Ulval.ca
- [2.] GHASARIAN, Christian, *De l'ethnographie à l'anthropologie réflexive, Nouveaux terrains, nouvelles pratiques, nouveaux enjeux*, Paris, Armand Colin Editeur, 2004.
- [3.] KABAMBI N., J.V., Cours de psychologie du consommateur et de vente, deuxième licence communication, Faculté des Lettres.
- [4.] KAPFERER, J.N., *Les chemins de la persuasion : mode d'influence des media et de la publicité sur les comportements*, Paris, Gauthier-Vilars, 1978.
- [5.] MULAMBA, N., *La lutte antitabac en RDC*, Mémoire, IFASIC ,1999-2000.
- [6.] News. Un. Org OMS : Seules des environnements 100 % sans fumée protègent efficacement contre les dangers du tabagisme passif, Consulté le 06-08-2022, 12h15.
- [7.] NKURUNZIZA, Diane, *L'impact de la propagande sur les électeurs lors de la campagne pour les présidentielles de 2011. Cas des communes de Limete et de Masina en RDC*, mémoire, L2, IFASIC, communication et journalisme, 2011-2012.
- [8.] PETROF, John V. *Comportement du consommateur et marketing*, 5e édition, Quebec, les presses de l'université LAVAL, 1993.
- [9.] SCAILLET, Stéphane, *Psychologie appliquée à l'éducation*, Paris, Franciscaine missionnaires de Marie, 1981.